

SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS AND STRUCTURAL PECULIARITIES OF SPORT PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract: – The article analyses the semantic features of phraseological units in sport. The purpose of the work is to study the phraseological units of a particular area of usage in sport. The objectives of the study are to identify thematic groups of phraseological units and defining their pragmatic goals in the genre of sports journalism as a kind of spontaneous public speech. Collected material can be used in linguistic and stylistic analysis of texts of various styles and genres. They are mainly considered to be the product of sport commentators' intelligence. We also write about the importance of the context while translating phraseological units. He claims that depending on the context the translation of the same phraseological units may differ. The author also explains the differences between sport phrases and terms using various sport matches. We come to the conclusion that the above-mentioned methods are very important while translating phraseological units. The importance of phraseological units, namely sport phrases and terms in the communication process relating to sport terminology has been stated in the article as well.

INTRODUCTION

In linguistics, there are such phraseological units that create the expressiveness and imagery of speech, and their appearance is strongly connected with people's views and attitudes towards objects and events in objective existence. The usage of phraseological units in the field of sports in oral and written communication is commonly scattered in Great Britain, USA, Australia and other English speaking countries. One of the main reasons is popular among the peoples of the world of sports competitions, the latter being England's own socio-political influence on the colonized states under its control.

The use of phraseological units enables excluding excessive formality and monotony of sports reports. Sports presenters on television use the phraseological diversity of the Russian language in their speech as a source of expression and emotional involvement, which is almost obligatory for sports reports.

We know that phraseological units and stylistic devices are such tools that increase the effectiveness of speech. Just as the study of phraseological and stylistic problems occupies an important place in the structure of linguistic and artistic text translations, today the study of special aspects of linguistics, in particular, from the point of view of terminological systems, is gaining relevance.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

While most of the English sport terms and phraseological units that have become popular from sports terminology continue to be expressed in their original form without changing their form, some phraseological units and terms are also being used in new meanings in Uzbek sport terminology. Phraseological units and terms in Uzbek sport terminology with such a stylistic color create some difficulties in the translation and interpretation of terms and phraseological units in the field of sports. Sports brought many new concepts and terms into the vocabulary of the Uzbek language and others.

Sports commentators try to do everything possible so that the viewer (or listener) becomes not only interested in the report but also experiences emotional stress. [Куранова Т.П., 2018:111-116]. This emotional background is characteristic of sports broadcasts. In order to ensure a high level of emotionality, commentators use phraseological units in their speech "The study of the relationship between terminology and phraseology is one of the new and urgent issues of modern linguistics" [Федуленкова Т.Н., Иванов А.И., Куприна Т.В, 2009: 23].

In the process of this research, we collected phrases in the field of sports literature, newspapers and magazines, and TV shows from English-speaking foreign countries. In addition, “English-Uzbek-Russian Dictionary of Sport Terms” published by H.Rafiev and Sh.Botayev (2015), It is worth nothing that we have found and analyzed expressions in the field of sports by A.V. Kunin’s book “Anglo-Russian Phraseological Dictionary”(1984) and А. Н. Блеер, ф. П. Суслов, д. А. Тышлер “Терминология спорта толковый словарь-справочник более 10 000 терминов”(2010). The next scientist, who investigated the same issue, was B.A.Larin. He argued that this branch of linguistics is still at the stage of registration as a full- fledged science, but he pointed out that, it is impossible to deny the necessity of singling out such a discipline. Professor B.A.Larin under the subject of phraseology demonstrated indissoluble, stable combinations, that is, close unity of several words, expressing a holistic view [Larin B.A, 1956: 22].

3. ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Phraseology is a well-studied linguistic discipline. The theoretical and methodological basis of the paper is comprised of the works of A.N. Baranov, V.V. Vinogradov, D.O. Dobrovolsky, V.P. Zhukov, V.M. Mokienko, V.N. Telia, A.I. Fedorov. We will rely on the narrow understanding of phraseological units, which defines them as units that are characterized by “idiomaticity, expressiveness, stability, reproducibility, imagery, nominative function”.[Рычкова Н.Г. 2017: 413]

Phraseologists emphasize that a phraseological unit “never arises immediately, at the very first moment of creation and use of its material composition”, it is “always the result of gradual formation”.[Амосова Н.Н. 1963: 360]

Ch.Bally’s theory which states that the main feature of a phraseological unit is possibility or impossibility to replace it by one single word.[Кунин А.В. 1999: 43]

The concept of ‘phraseologic unit (unite phraseologique) has been first used by Charles Bally, wherefrom it was taken by V.V. Vinogradov and other Soviet linguists, who translated it by ‘frazelogiceskaja edinita’. He defines them as ready-made language units that are taken from one generation to another and are used in the process of speech as traditional word combinations. Shansky defines phraseologisms as ‘frozen patterns of language that consist of two or more components and allow little or no variation in form, structure or meaning’.

Another classification in which there are two principles applied is established by N.Amosova. She distinguishes two types of phraseological units:

phrasemes (units of fixed context in which one of the components has specialized meaning dependent on the second component, e.g., small talk, fair sex);

idioms (idioms are semantically and grammatically inseparable units, e.g., play with fire).[Амосова Н.Н. 1963: 360]

Classifications of phraseological units:

A.J.Smirnitsky classifies phraseological units according to their stylistic features:

phraseological units (stylistically neutral, with faded metaphorical motivation, e.g., be in love, fall in love);

idioms (they are based on metaphor, they are emotionally and stylistically coloured, e.g., cool as a cucumber).[Smirnitsky A.I. 1996: 153]

According to A.V.Kunin, the phraseological units mean the understanding that the meanings of their structural components are interrelated with the synchronic aspect [Кунин А.В, 1964: 58]. In this meaning, phraseological units appear in a form in accordance with the spirit, mentality, life experience and tradition of the nation, carry a portable meaning based on words with a special meaning along with the meanings and structural construction of the components contained in it.

In the field of sports, there are such phraseological units that undergo certain evolutionary periods. When analyzed historically, the process of gradual development of such phraseological units emerges. One such example is the playbook unit. Historical sources show that the British have long been considered pious people, and almost all families had books that defined, demonstrated, and explained their religious practices. This book is called the pray(er) book.

It has been used in the sports field since 1965 in a figurative meaning. In the sport, the playbook is a guide that expresses the strategic instructions of the coach. Currently, there are written, magnetic board, and electronic versions of them. Playbook in Uzbek is used as a neologism by sports journalists without the article. These phraseological units are often observed during comments by English-speaking journalists. For example: Being in coach Shanahan's system and learning the playbook, that's really the hardest thing (Dieter Kurtenbach) - Shanaxan tizimida murabbiylik qilish va o'yin kitobini o'rganish, bu haqiqatan ham eng qiyin narsa.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Taking into account the comparative analysis of different classifications of phraseological units which the author has observed, she has to admit that the following classification worked out by A.V. Kunin can be considered the most detailed one. He has critically examined most of the existing classifications and elaborated his own classification of phraseological units which is based on more thorough analysis of these phenomena of language. In his classification A.V. Kunin keeps a close watch to the elements of phraseology which have not been emphasized by other researchers, as well as takes into consideration also the development of the English language. Since A.V. Kunin's classification of phraseological units is grounded on wide theoretical and practical material concerning different languages, the author of the present article assumes that this classification could be applied also to the phraseological systems of other languages.

Kunin has worked out a structural-semantic classification, which reveals the function of a phraseological unit depending on its size (collocations or sentences).

Although these phraseological expressions are not small in number, they have allowed us to identify and explain lexical-semantic, structure-functional features of English-language sports terms. During the course of the research, phraseological units can be categorized into several types of sports, which are noted in modern English, as well as in sports.

1. The phraseological units which are directly related to show etymology of physical education and sport For example: Shoot the ball into one's own goal - score the ball into own goal (football). Get to first base – the first step towards success, the first step (baseball). Hit below the belt – to hit the lower part of the belt, using the trick (boxing). [Кунин А. В. 1984: 944]

2. The phraseological units which are indirectly related to show etymology of physical education and sport. For example: Also ran – loser, participant in sports contests who failed in the competitions. Example, English: I'm afraid he'll always be one of life's rans – Uzbek translation: Афсуски, унинг ҳеч қачон иши юришмайди (омади чопмайди) – Russian: Я боюсь, что он всегда будет неудачником.

3. In the third group we collected phraseological unit that “Half parts belongs Sport sphere”. With such phraseological units, no idea about the etymology and origin of sports types. The majority of these are not just sports compound words today, but also the combined lexemes in the social, military, navy, and empty fields. Examples: To catch the card – to fish, to dive deep; head to head – to fight hard and with courage (english: the governor and the senator went head to head in a spontaneous debate – uzbek translation: губернатор ва сенатор режалаштирилмаган мунозара (дебат)да матонат билан кураш олиб борди, охиригача курашмоқ, “ё ҳаёт ё мамот” шиори остида курашмоқ; to win hands down – to win easily (english: The other team are two men short, in theory, at least, we ought to win hands down – uzbek translation: Бошқа жамоаларда икки ўйинчи етишмаяпди, биз уларни осонликча ютиш эҳтимолимиз бор. – russian; У другой команды не хватает двух игроков. По всей вероятности, мы должны легко выиграть).

The use of phraseological units in oral and written discourses is shaped by specific extralegalistic factors, that are, interactions with specific sports, sporting events and events that reflect specific situations and events.

Although the lexical units that make up the phraseological expressions are free lexemes separately, they are portable when translated from one language to another, and it is advisable to find and translate their alternatives. There are also such expressions in the English language as in the field of physical culture and sports, which may be said to have been formed by the combination of other words in the same word.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

From the above examples, it became clear that the translation of phraseological units related to physical education and sports from one language to another is one of the important tasks. In this sense, we considered it permissible to touch on the methods of translating phraseological units related to the sport field during the research process. In this article, while analyzing English sports phrases and terms, we studied the characteristics of their absorption in Uzbek sports terminology and how they are used in the language. In current day, one of the important tasks of modern linguistics which is not only the classification and description of English phraseological units and terms, but also their comparative and contrastive scientific analysis and translation issues.

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